

LIVED EXPERIENCES OF COUPLES WHO ATTENDED THE MARRIAGE ENCOUNTER WEEKEND PROGRAM: A PHENOMENOLOGICAL STUDY

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ABSTRACT

The Marriage Encounter Week-end Seminar was developed in response to a need for better knowledge and appreciation of God's design for marriage and family life, and it is now a part of the Catholic Church. Couples must spend time in an atmosphere where God's word can be read, understood, and meditated on; where couples can come before the Lord and present themselves as a live oblation to understand God's purpose more clearly and personally. A period of reflection is required for couples to evaluate themselves, their relationship, their family life, and their roles in the framework of God's plan. Couples require time to understand God's vision and to make real efforts to achieve it. With these, this research was made to investigate the lived experiences of couples who attended the Marriage Encounter Week-End Seminar. The research is based on James Fowler's Faith stage theory, which was produced after he examined and developed a stage theory for religious faith formation. The study employed phenomenology as a qualitative research method. Furthermore, the study found that the couple's experiences opened the road for them to bring their entire family to church every Sunday and couples who participated in this study revealed that it is a helpful tool

for encouraging couples to join the Family Life Apostolate (FALA) or the Basic Ecclesial Community (BEC).

Keywords: *Marriage Encounter, Week-end Seminar, Marriage, Family, FALA, BEC*

INTRODUCTION

The first "Encuentro Conjugal" was organized in 1962 by Father Gabriel Calvo, who gathered together 28 couples from factory workers in Spain. The movement came out of the Christian Family Movement's structure (CFM). In 1996, the Marriage Encounter (ME) was introduced to Latin America, and in 1967, it was introduced to Miami, Florida, USA, and Mexico. Luisito and Asuncion Sison attended the International Confederation of the Christian Family Movement (CFM) congress in Southern Indiana in the summer of 1969. A week later, they went to a Marriage Encounter weekend. That same year, the three of them organized a team and brought the Christian Family Movement's apostolic program to the Philippines (CFM). On October 3-5, 1969, the Loyola Retreat House in Angono, Rizal hosted the inaugural ME Weekend in the Philippines, which was led by Fr. Ruben Tanseco, S.J. is a Jesuit priest who is a member of the Society of Jesus. as a Team Priest and as a Team Couple, Sito-Sony Sison. The class Number 1 MEWS was comprised of eleven (11) couples and four (4) priests. Adaptations have been made to meet our people's and our culture's demands (Marriage Encounter Foundation of the Philippines-MEFP).

The first MEW was held in Tacloban in 1973, on the initiative of the Christian Family Movement, which was just getting started in the city. This was done again in 1977 as a way to bring in new members to the CFM. Finally, in 1988, Toting Solis, the president of Our Lady of Lourdes Parish, stepped down.

Only when an organization's vision statement is established can it gain a feeling of direction. The ultimate reason for an organization's existence is its vision. It is an ideal state of being that every member should aspire towards, even if it is unlikely to be achieved in one's lifetime. "We, the people of the Archdiocese of Palo, foresee being a people of God, a community of disciples, fed by God's word and sacraments, proclaiming to gospel principles and celebrating the Christ event of liberation for the fulfillment of His kingdom in the Archdiocese," the vision states (The 1995 Archdiocesan Pastoral Plan).

The 1995 Archdiocesan Pastoral Plan states that one of the mission statements is to "build, strengthen, and sustain Christian community life and share in diverse forms of service, especially for the poor." The project leader for this study is the coordinator of the Family and Life Apostolate (FALA) of Saint Vincent Ferrer Parish, Babatngon, Leyte. The Archdiocese's Family and Life Apostolate is the implementing arm of the Catholic Bishops Conference of the Philippines' (CBCP) Episcopal Commission on Family and Life (ECFL), and operates following the First Archdiocese Pastoral Assembly Decree. It follows the thrust of the Local and Universal Church, guided by the teaching of the Church's Magisterium.

The said commission was established in the parish of Babatngon on July 25, 2016. One of the major activities undertaken by the recruited couples was to attend the Marriage Encounter Weekend Seminar (MEWS), where the project leader had previously served as Team Speaker of the said seminar in various towns throughout Leyte and Samar before serving as couple coordinator of the FALA in Babatngon, Leyte.

Our encountering families are invited to establish themselves in the places where they truly belong—their parishes, dioceses, and countries. Their ME group or class, their ME sector, or foundation is just a way for them to reach out, a "refilling station" for spiritual formation and growth. As a result, the ME apostolate as a whole is a means to serve the local church rather than an end in itself (Fr. Tanseco,1982).

The preceding paragraphs, along with the project proponent's observation, cleared the path for the study's completion. The findings of this research will be provided to the appropriate Catholic sector, specifically at the parish level, for referral to the proper authority for policy redirection, augmentation, and amendment.

Domains of Inquiry

This study aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What are the lived experiences of couples who attended the two-day Marriage Encounter Week-end Seminar (MEWS)?
2. What is the essence of their experiences on relationship satisfaction?

Theoretical Framework of the Study

The study is based on Sadia Mehmod's book Narrative Theory, which came out on July 11, 2013. Narrative is a sort of discourse that weaves together a variety of events, occurrences, and human acts (Polkinghome,1995). It is defined by Creswell as "a study of experiences" as "individuals' lived and reported stories" (Creswell,2010).

Narrative researchers gather stories, documentation, and group discussions concerning one or two people's lived and recounted experiences. They capture the stories through interviews, observations, records, and photos, then report on the events and order the meaning of those events chronologically. Narrative research methodology is described as "casual data collecting" rather than a strict process.

METHODOLOGY

The study employed phenomenology as a qualitative research method. The phenomenological approach highlights the specific, identifying phenomena based on how the actors in a situation perceive them. In the human realm, this typically entails acquiring "deep" knowledge and perspectives through inductive qualitative methods such as interviews, discussions, and participant observation, and then expressing it from the perspective of the study participant (s). Phenomenology is the study of

experience from the individual's perspective, "bracketing" commonly held beliefs and ways of viewing reality (Neubauer BE, Witkop CT, Varpio L.. 2019).

The study was participated by seven (7) couples who attended the Marriage Encounter Weekend Seminar held in Saint Vincent Ferrer Parish, Babatngon, Leyte on September 16-17, 2016. These couples were the first to be identified as belonging to Class 1 of the eight (8) MEWS classes that had previously been held in the town. Class I was chosen as the study's responders since they were the first to attend the seminar. Similarly, the researchers want to know if the seminar had an impact on their relationship as a pair and what changes they experienced from that time to now.

To collect the data for this study, the researchers obtained permission from the couples, made them sign the informed consent forms prepared by the researchers and were oriented of the research objectives and purpose of the study. They were invited to the project leader's home, where the interview was conducted to obtain the data needed using the prepared questionnaire. Each pair was allocated to a specific interviewer, who conducted the interview using a set of pre-written questions as a guide. Each pair was asked six (6) different questions. Before each the interview starts, the interviewer informs the research participants that the interview will be recorded. They were given the assurance that everything will be treated with utmost confidentiality and the transcripts shall be shown to them for their validation before they are treated for analysis and discussion. The recorded responses of the participants were transcribed, assigned code and themes, and analyzed, following the specific procedures as described by Moustakas.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The researchers used the coding procedure to find the themes of the individuals' lived experiences, considering the diverse and hidden meanings underlying their lived experiences. Coding is the process of identifying concepts or ideas that interest couples' lived experiences following their participation in the two-day Marriage Encounter Weekend Seminar.

The following themes arose from the participants' accounts of their experiences: (1) a refreshed person, (2) closeness in their relationship as a couple, (3) intimacy of the couple with their children and other family members, and (4) connection of the complete family to God.

A Renewed Person. One of the experiences revealed by the participants after attending the two-day Marriage Encounter Weekend Seminar is becoming a renewed person as revealed in the following lines:

Waray hinihipos ngadi, nga kon bisan masakit ha kuan dire mo na ma-aalangan ha iya kay nabaruan namon dida han MEWS na mas maupay it pagsusurat hin love letter, nga diin mas maupay hiya, epektibo kaysa magyayakan ka hin verbal.[No hidden grudges from each other though truth hurts, in this way we become more comfortable, and as we have learned from

Marriage Encounter Weekend Seminar it is better to write a love letter because it is more effective than verbal].

Dire na gihap madali maaringit.[Not easily irritated.] (Transcript 3,page 3 , Line132)

Dire ko na ginbibiling iton nga pag-iinom. [Not longing for alcoholic drinks] (Transcript 3, page 4, Line 138)

Nakikigsocialize. [Learn how to mingle with others](Transcript 4, page 5, Line 96)

Natutong magrespeto sa aking asawa [Learned how to respect my husband/wife] (Transcript 1, page 2, Lines 203-204)

Nautod na an akon mga bisyo. [I stopped my vices.] (Transcript 5, page 6, Lines 223)

Nalipay na kami nga duwa kay humalawig na amon pasensya ha kada tagsa . [We became happier and have more patience with each other] (Transcript 5,page 6 Line 247)

Communication as a vital facet of the family processes has been receiving increasing prominence in the field of family relations (Bienvenu, 2014). Many authorities believe that good communication is the key to sound family interaction and the lifeblood of all marital relationships. A study entitled, Measurement of Marital Communication revealed significant contrasts in patterns and degrees of communication. Elements differentiating between good and poor communication in couples are the handling of anger and of differences, tone of voice, understanding, good listening habits, and self-disclosure. It was found that understanding components of healthy communication in marital interaction are indeed paramount to marital success. The experiences shared by the participants show that marriage in the truest sense of the word, is possible. The couples' testimonies strengthen the prime reason why the organization was founded in 1962 by Father Gabriel Calvo. Indeed, when two people decide to live as one and enter into married life, a considerable adjustment in all aspects of their lives need to be changed. As changes are meant to be unpleasant, any manifestation of these are deserving of appreciation. Everyone understands that changing a person is a difficult task. To become a better or rejuvenated person, it requires a lot of time, work, and courage. As a result, Marriage Encounter can be deduced as a potent tool for changing a person's attitude and behavior.

Closeness in their Relationship as a Couple. Another experience revealed by the participants were their closeness as a couple, revealed on the preceding lines :

Damo ini nga nabag-o, kon paano kami magkuan yana hit amon kamag-asawa kon бага paano kami magkaintindahay hit tagsa-tagsa nga mga sayop ha mag-asawa . [There are many changes in our lives as couple, as to how we understand our weaknesses as a couple] (Transcript 1, page1, Line 28-29).

Mas lalo namon naintindihan ko nano gud it dapat o angay himuon ht mag-asawa nga diri magkaada hin samok hit pamilya. [We became more understanding as to how we manage our family feud] (Transcript 1, page 2, Lines 203-204)

Higugmaon ko hin duro an akon asawa[I love my wife very much]
(Transcript 1, page 5, Lines 223)

Sugad man liwat higugmaon ko gihapon an akon bana [Likewise, I love my husband very much] (Transcript 1, page 5, Line 224)

Awdanon kami nga tipo pero nawara an amon kaawdanon tungod nga kinahanglanon kada miting maatender manggud kon namimiembro ka na hit ME. [Timid and hesitant first but in the long run we manage to face people since we are required to attend meetings every now and then once you became a member of ME]

(Transcript 5, page 6, Lines 239-241) [

Mas naging close kami ngan mas naging open na kami para pag-iro-storyahan an mga bagay-bagay [We became closer and open to each other on many things and other issues] (Transcript 6, page 6, Lines 271-272).

These findings are in consonance with the study, Effects of Relationship Education on Couple Communication and Satisfaction. Although the participants in the cited study were not members of any religious organization for married couples, the findings clearly show that couples who become members of organizations and whose objectives are to strengthen a married couple's relationship can enhance and strengthen it and intervention, in the form of counselling through communication and dialogues, has profound positive effects on relationship satisfaction (Williamson, H. C., Altman, N., Hsueh, J., & Bradbury, T. N. 2016)

Closeness of the couple with their children and other Members of the Family. Another theme that was identified was the closeness of the couple with their children and the other members in the family. This can be observed in the following lines:

Tapos an ira relasyon naiba ha ira mga anak. Maaram na hira magaram-aram, maaram na hira umintindi hit ira mga anak, dako it nabulig hit nga ME, dako it nabag-o [The relationship with their children changed. With the help of Marriage Encounter, they learned how to care and understand them better] (Transcript 2, page 3, Lines 94-95)

Ahhh... naalagaan ang mga anak, naakay nai-min sa mabuting landas patungo sa panginoon. Sabay-sabay kaming nagsisimba. [Ahhh... we were able to take care and guide our chilgren closer to God. We go to church together.] (Transcript 4, page 4, lines 163-164)

Sa akin naging maupay ako hindi lang sa aking pamilya, sa mga anak ko at pati mga taong nakapaligid sa amin Malaki ang naging respeto ko dati na hindi ko ginagawa [I became a better person not only to my family, my children and to the people who surrounds us, I became respectful unlike before.] (Transcript 4, page 5, lines 191-192)

The above-mentioned responses from the participants provided a clear picture of how attendance to the Marriage Encounter influenced the parent's interactions with their children and other family members. It cannot be denied that a considerable effort is needed to keep relationships within a family smooth. Even more effort is required to enhance and affirm the strengths in a family. Certain contributions each family member can make to help create a stronger and more satisfying family life which include factors like a satisfying marriage relationship, sharing family power, open family communications, acceptance and appreciation of each other, quality time together, conflict management; and a good family spirit. With the participants' regular attendance to Marriage Encounter, they (participants) were somehow reoriented to the importance of fostering better family relationships and took more effort in satisfying the factors needed to strengthen their respective families. These, were evidenced by their unwavering concern and devotion to their children. Respect was gained, meaningful time with the family was spent, and most importantly, faith and love of God were implanted in their children's minds (Combs, C. W., Bufford, R. K., Campbell, C. D., & Halter, L. L. (2000).

Closeness of the couple and the Whole Family to God. One of the most noteworthy testimonies shared by the participants after attendance to the two-day weekend seminars is the apparent strengthening and development of their relationship with God. The participants felt drawn to more to God, which, were exhibited more in their affection towards their entire family, that in turn drew them to God. These were expressed in the preceding lines:

Ito na ME nakapadugang-dugang ito hiya ha amon. May power it Ginoo. [ME strengthened more our faith in God. God is powerful] (Transcript 1, page2, line 55)

Naabat ko opportunity na tumubo ang ano ko sa Panginoon dahil magaan ang pakiramdam ko hindi na ako yung taong mainitin ang ulo natuto akong mag respeto sa aking asawa ko sa mga anak ko kasama ko sa bahay lalo na sa Panginoon na araw-araw hindi ko malimutan ang magsimba sa Sto.Niño Church. {I felt that God grew in our lives us we felt in a positive change in our dealing with each other as to my children and the rest of my family member often attend mass at Sto.Niño Church (Transcript 4,Page 5,Lines 202-205).

So kuan ko na ada hi Lord ha amon naging close kami kasi nagbuburubligay kami. [God has been the center of our lives, we became closer we help each other](Transcript 4 ,page 5,Lines 208-209)

Nahipasa ha amon mga anak an oryentasyon nga kada Domingo masimba pero an akon asawa diri gud nasimba. Maupay nala kay nalamragan gihapon hiya han Ginoo. [We were able to pass on to our children the practice of going to church every Sunday and so with my husband who was enlightened by God] (Trascript 5,page 6, Line 239)

It can be surmised that the Marriage Encounter Weekend Seminars had an influence not only on the participants but also on the couples' children as well when it comes to fostering better relationships with God. These are evidenced by their testimonies as one of the activities and experiences shared in the MEWS is the teachings of God. After all, the organization was founded by a priest, anchored on the teachings of the Holy Bible and Christianity. The experience gave the participants insight on the importance of spending time to bond with their families which could bring them closer to God. Further, many couples believe they have gained considerably much from the Marriage Encounter experience.

Conclusions

It cannot be overemphasized how the role of families is paramount to nation-building. Strengthening the family, the most basic unit of the society is where the country's hope for progress and development is hinged on. It is thus imperative for couples to acknowledge their roles as husband and wife to each other, as well as their responsibility to their respective families and communities such as church-related activities like the MEW to provide substantial contribution in the upbringing of the youth. As couples become more aware of their responsibilities as a husband/wife and parents to their children, their bond become stronger, and their respective families become better. Further, as the couple's children witness the love and respect shared by their parents to each other manifest, their children too become more loving, caring, and understanding as well.

Recommendations

From the testimonies of the participants, it can thus be claimed that participation to the Marriage Encounter Week-end Seminar (MEWS) is an effective tool for encouraging couples to join the Family and Life Apostolate (FALA) or the Basic Ecclesial Community (BEC). It is believed that when couples are rejuvenated as what the MEW is meant to achieve, couples are turned into better people/parents, thus, that it will be easier for them to bring their children and other family members to church.

Compliance With Ethical Standards

The respondents voluntarily participated to the research study conducted by the researchers from Eastern Visayas State University. The respondents understand that the research is designed to gather the data for the study. They were allowed to ask questions about the project and their participation. Moreover, the use of the data in

research, publication, sharing and archiving has been explained thoroughly. They further agreed that taking part in the project would include being interviewed and recorded (Audio or Video) provided that their identity are kept confidential and they have the freedom to withdraw anytime. After the data were transcribed and confirmed by the respondents, the recordings were destroyed.

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